

USE OF DIDACTIC EXHIBITIONS IN NATURAL SCIENCE TEACHING

Avazmetova Intizor Rajabbayevna

Urgench State University

Teacher of the Department of Preschool Education Methodology

Rustamova Farangiz Rustam qizi

Yo'ldasheva Madinabonu Shonazar qizi

Urgench State University

4th year students of primary education and sports education

Shuhratova Oymonjon Shuhrat qizi

Urgench State University

Biology 1st year student

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Abstract: Different methods are used in teaching students. As a result, students will be able to acquire more knowledge. In this article, we can see the use of didactic exhibitions in the teaching of natural sciences on the example of elementary school students.

Key words: practical methods, scientific subjects, didactic materials, pedagogue, foreign experience, intellectual potential, teaching of natural sciences as a separate subject starts from the 1st grade. In the textbooks, which are considered educational material, books combining the topics of "Natural objects", "Plant and animal world", "We will save our health" and "Ecology" are taught.

The program on natural sciences allows schoolchildren of younger age to learn not only the beauty and wealth of nature, but also the nature of our republic. In the teaching of natural sciences, attention is paid to the formation and expansion of students' scientific and natural worldviews, and to the explanation of the topic of each lesson in teaching logical thinking. In the process of students' individual performance of tasks, their mental activity is involved, confidence in their knowledge, strength and abilities increases. As a result, each person develops at the level of their potential. Time is effectively used in cognitive activities organized in this way. As a result, the effectiveness of education increases. Students' cognitive activities are organized individually in lessons conducted using modern pedagogical technologies of education. If the students are taught with the help of modern methods, the students' acceptance of learning increases greatly, which has been tested by many researchers. Along with theoretical knowledge, practice plays an important role in the formation of young professional qualities of students. 99 Natural scientific knowledge has been acquired for many years due to practical activities. Knowledge does not appear

in people's brains by itself, but is formed in certain work activities. Practice is the main factor in a person's relationship with nature, which, in turn, plays an important role in the system of people's mutual relations and social production. The main types of practice are material production and scientific experience. Scientific - natural practice performs the following tasks. For example, knowledge taught in practice will allow students to understand more things than theoretical lessons.

As the relevance of the topic, the method of using didactic visual aids is the most convenient, effective and understandable method that has been used since ancient times. Studying using didactic handouts, i.e. by seeing with the eyes, conveys much more information to the brain 5 times more than hearing and 13 times more than tactical organs. Therefore, it is appropriate to teach students through didactic games and programs starting from primary grades. As for foreign experience, the newest methods of education are used in foreign countries. There are even schools where students only learn by doing. Theoretical information can be learned only by themselves. In conclusion, it is no exaggeration to say that it is possible to develop the thinking ability of students by using didactic exhibitions in the teaching of natural sciences. For example, if a group is selected to conduct an experiment in a school through the development of a methodical recommendation, and lessons are conducted using didactic materials, and lessons are given to other classes based on the same curriculum as usual. As a result, the students of the selected class will learn much more than their peers in the other group.

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